

POLYPHENOLS: HEALTH AND THERAPEUTIC BENEFITS FROM PLANTS

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ABSTRACT

Polyphenols are natural compounds that are important for human health and are known for multiple health benefits. These compounds are characterized by their diverse application and play an important role in the prevention of chronic diseases and the strengthening of overall health. Research has shown that polyphenols can reduce oxidative stress and protect cellular integrity, contributing to a reduced risk of diseases such as cancer and cardiovascular disorders, and are also effective in managing inflammation and beneficial in treating various medical conditions. The diversity of applications of polyphenols underscores their importance as promising therapeutics in the health sector, and this paper highlights aspects of the importance of these compounds.

Keywords: Polyphenols, health benefits, chronic diseases, oxidative stress, inflammation, overall health, treatment.

1/ INTRODUCTION

Polyphenols are a group of phytochemical compounds that contain a hydroxyl group (-OH) attached to one or more benzene rings, distinguishing them from other phenolic compounds. Polyphenols are characterized by the presence of multiple benzene units in their structure, with an estimated 8,000 different types of polyphenols found in plants. These compounds are water-soluble and polar, meaning they dissolve in aqueous fluids and are easily absorbed by the body. Polyphenols are part of the secondary metabolites of plants, playing a role in protecting the plant from environmental threats such as ultraviolet rays, pests, and fungi. [1]

Polyphenols possess various biological properties, most notably their antioxidant activity. Free radicals generated from metabolic processes can damage cells and tissues, increasing the risk of degenerative diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, and neurological disorders. Polyphenols act as powerful antioxidants, interacting with free radicals and neutralizing their harmful effects, thus helping to reduce the damage caused by oxidative stress. Furthermore, polyphenols have anti-inflammatory properties, as they combat the inflammatory response by inhibiting enzymes linked to these processes, such as cyclooxygenase, thereby reducing the likelihood of chronic diseases associated with inflammation.

Scientific studies have shown that polyphenols play a crucial role in preventing neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases. They reduce the effects of free radicals on nerve cells and enhance brain function by stimulating cellular repair processes and reducing neuroinflammation. These effects make polyphenols a significant area of research in the field of treatment and prevention of diseases affecting the central nervous system.

Polyphenols also show multiple health benefits related to metabolism. Research has shown that consuming polyphenols enhances insulin sensitivity and lowers blood sugar levels, which helps in the prevention of type 2 diabetes. In addition, studies indicate that these compounds can contribute to improving cardiovascular health through antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects that reduce the risk of coronary artery disease.

Due to these various properties, polyphenols are considered important compounds in the fields of preventive medicine and natural therapy. They can be used as dietary supplements or developed into drugs to enhance the prevention of chronic diseases and improve overall health.[1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8]

2/ CLASSIFICATION OF POLYPHENOLS

Polyphenols are chemical compounds produced exclusively through the shikimate/phenylpropanoid pathway and/or the polyketide pathway. These compounds consist of multiple phenolic units and do not contain nitrogen groups. The classification of polyphenols primarily depends on the structure of the phenolic ring, as well as the side chains or associated molecules. Based on this diversity in chemical structure and bioavailability, polyphenols are classified into several types, with the main types as follows:[7][9][10]

Figure 1 Main categories of polyphenols[10]

2/1-PHENOLIC ACIDS

Phenolic acids are characterized by unique structural properties, possessing a single phenolic ring, unlike other compounds. This group resembles phenolic compounds, structured with a single carboxylic acid group and one or more hydroxyl derivatives. Therefore, they are primarily associated with amides, esters, and glycosides [1]. Due to the presence of both carboxylic acid and phenolic hydroxyl groups, phenolic acids exhibit acidic and weakly basic properties, as well as the electron-loving properties of phenols [4].

There are two main groups of phenolic acids: hydroxybenzoic acid and hydroxycinnamic acid. Hydroxybenzoic acid primarily consists of a carbonyl group, a carboxyl group, and a hydroxyl group. Its main derivatives include gallic acid (GA), tannic acid (TA), protocatechuic acid, and para-hydroxybenzoic acid. In contrast, hydroxycinnamic acid is characterized by a benzene ring, an acrylic acid group, a hydroxyl group, and an aldehyde group within its structure. Hydroxycinnamic acid is more widespread than hydroxybenzoic acid, with derivatives including coumaric acid, ferulic acid (FA), caffeic acid (CA), and rosmarinic acid [1,4].(Fig. 4B)

Phenolic acids are present in a variety of foods, especially herbs, vegetables, grains, fruits, legumes, and beverages. These compounds exhibit antioxidant activity by donating hydrogen atoms, making them beneficial in the prevention of degenerative diseases [1,4,8,9].

Gallic acid is one of the essential phenolic acids, possessing high bioavailability. It has been shown to be present in plasma and urine after consumption, with studies indicating protective effects of phenolic acids against degenerative diseases. For example, Caliorra et al. noted the bioavailability and pharmacokinetics of gallic acid in relatively healthy humans. In this study, 125 ml of Assam black tea was prepared to 200 ml with distilled water and consumed orally; the tea contained 50 mg of free gallic acid, which was found at concentrations of 0.30 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ and 0.15 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ in plasma and urine, respectively [8].

Phenolic acids are biologically active due to their structure. Mushrooms have been reported as a significant source of phenolic acids, explaining their therapeutic effects as antioxidants, antimicrobials, and antitumor agents. Studies indicate that phenolic acids are rapidly absorbed and metabolized in the intestines and stomach, with metabolism occurring in the small intestine and liver, resulting in methylated, glucuronidated, and sulfated compounds in biological fluids [1,4,8,9].

Figure 2 Chemical structure of the subclasses of phenolic acids, examples of compounds belonging to each subclass and examples of foodstuff containing them. The most abundant hydroxycinnamic acid found in food is chlorogenic acid (CGA), which is an ester formed between caffeic and quinic acids. On another hand, the most common hydroxybenzoic acids are gallic, vanillic, ellagic, syringic, p-hydroxybenzoic, and protocatechuic acids. [11]

2/2-Flavonoids

Flavonoids are the most researched and well-known class of polyphenols. The basic structure of a flavonoid consists of two aromatic rings with a three-carbon chain containing one oxygen atom, forming an oxidized heterocyclic ring. This class of polyphenols can be divided into several subgroups depending on the oxidation state of the central carbon [1]. Generally, the abundance of phenolic hydroxyl groups in flavonoid molecules makes them soluble in alkaline aqueous solutions, as well as in solvents such as pyridine, formamide, and dimethylformamide [4].

Flavonoids are divided into six different classes: flavanols, flavonols, isoflavones, flavanones, flavones, and anthocyanidins. Known as secondary metabolites in certain plant structures (fruits and seeds), flavonoids are essential for their ability to provide color, taste, and aroma. This diverse group of polyphenols includes a wide range of different varieties and is among the most studied categories in botany. Flavonoids, which play a complementary role in plant metabolism, facilitate growth and also contribute to protective mechanisms. Additionally, this class plays a significant role in reducing the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in plants under stress, as they can regulate ROS activity. Consequently, flavonoids contribute to a variety of potentially bioactive functions that enhance human health, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, cardiovascular protective, neuroprotective, anticancer, and anti-aging effects [1].

The bioavailability of flavonoids is generally low, despite their health-promoting promises, and can vary significantly across different groups and individual compounds within a given class. The relative urinary excretion of daidzein and anthocyanin has been estimated at approximately 43% and 0.3%, respectively, explaining the variability in flavonoid bioavailability. Numerous laboratory and clinical trials are underway to determine the bioavailability of flavonoid compounds. In a study conducted by Aziz et al., volunteers consumed onions containing a high amount of conjugated quercetin (139 mg), resulting in a plasma concentration of 1.34 mmol and a urinary excretion rate of 0.8%. A single dose of pure flavonoid glycoside crystals, present in 500 mg of naringenin mixed in 240 ml of water, resulted in a urinary excretion rate of 4.9% [8].

Figure 3 Chemical structure of the main subclasses of flavonoids, examples of compounds belonging to each subclass and examples of foodstuff containing them. The largest subgroup of flavonoids are flavanols, in which the hydroxyl group is positioned in the C3 of the C ring. Flavanones and flavones display a hydroxyl group in the C5 of the A ring with the difference between them residing in the double bond formed between positions 2 and 3, which is saturated in flavanones. Isoflavones differ from flavones on the position of the phenyl group, being structurally similar to estrogens. Flavanonols present the hydroxyl group linked to the C ring in the position 3, and no double bond between this and position 2. Anthocyanin hydroxyl groups of the A and C rings is what dictates their color. All subclasses can be found in fruits and vegetables. . [11]

2/3-STILBENES

This class of polyphenols is characterized by two aromatic rings connected by a methylene bridge and constitutes a large group of non-flavonoid phytochemicals. Stilbenes are also a type of phenylpropanoid, featuring a 1,2-diphenylethylene core [1]. The most common representative compound is resveratrol, which has been a particular focus of study, showing numerous biological functions, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antiproliferative activities. Researchers have conducted clinical and pharmacological studies to determine the bioavailability of stilbenes. A study on 500 mg of resveratrol in humans showed a plasma concentration of 0.28% [8].

Stilbenes synthesized via the phenylpropanoid pathway are also a class of natural organic molecules distributed in fruits and other plant sources. Stilbene compounds are primarily found in *Vitis vinifera*, *Arachis hypogaea*, *Sorghum bicolor*, *Polygonum cuspidatum*, *Rhodomyrtus tomentosa*, *Rheum undulatum*, *Melaleuca leucadendron*, and *Euphorbia lagascae*. They are among the compounds that provide plants with protection against viruses and other microbe-related attacks. Pinosylvin is present in significant quantities in the heartwood of pine trees.

Stilbenes have a record of low bioavailability; however, they are distributed across various tissues in the form of glucuronides and sulfate conjugates in tissues and plasma. Among these, glucuronide has been found to be the predominant metabolite, and its formation is rapid. Oral absorption of resveratrol in humans is approximately 75%; however, its bioavailability is found to be only 1%. About 90% of resveratrol undergoes fermentation by gut microbiota. After absorption, resveratrol conjugates enter systemic circulation and penetrate target tissues to carry out their physiological actions. Clinical trials have found that the high metabolic breakdown of resveratrol into resveratrol-3-O-sulfate, resveratrol-4'-O-glucuronide, and resveratrol-3-O-glucuronide limits its use in pharmaceutical applications.

Numerous research studies have been conducted to improve the bioavailability, solubility, and stability of stilbenes. The bioavailability of rhaponticin, a methylated derivative of resveratrol, was enhanced by modifying liposomes with polyethylene glycol, which reduced its distribution in the digestive system and increased plasma concentration by 4.5 times. Piceatannol, a monomeric derivative of resveratrol, showed a higher absorption rate (with a 2.6-fold higher maximum serum concentration) and better metabolic stability (higher area under the curve) than resveratrol. Oxyresveratrol has been shown to be less bioavailable than resveratrol, undergoing extensive hepatic metabolism before excretion in bile and urine. Thus, the bioavailability of stilbenes largely depends on their structure [9,1].

2/4-TANNIN

Tannin is a unique phenolic compound with a molecular weight ranging from 500 daltons to 30,000 daltons, typically classified into two main types: hydrolyzable tannins and condensed tannins [9][10]. Hydrolyzable tannins are characterized by a polyol core (such as D-glucose and quinic acid) attached to phenolic acids such as gallic acid and ellagic acid. Notable examples of this type of tannin include gallotannins and ellagitannins, each distinguished by the structural unit of gallic acid and ellagic acid, respectively. Hydrolyzable tannins can be easily broken down through ester bond cleavage under mild alkaline or acidic conditions or by enzymatic action.

Condensed tannins, such as proanthocyanidins, are formed by the condensation of flavan-3-ol units (such as catechins) with C4-C8 or C4-C6 bonds. Proanthocyanidins can be divided into two types: A and B. Type B proanthocyanidins have C4-C8 or C4-C6 bonds, while type A proanthocyanidins feature C2-C7 bonds. Tannins exhibit antioxidant activity that may surpass that of traditional antioxidants such as vitamin C or α -tocopherol. Moreover, the structure of tannins significantly influences their antioxidant activity, with an increase in polymerization enhancing the compound's ability to scavenge free radicals [10]. Tannins are found in many plant-based foods and beverages and can be either water-soluble or insoluble, depending on their molecular weight. Based on their chemical structure, tannins are classified into condensed tannins, hydrolyzable tannins, fluorotannins, and complex tannins. The shikimate pathway is considered the biosynthetic route for generating tannins. Some well-known tannins include gallotannins, ellagitannins, and proanthocyanidins [9].

2/5-Lignans

Lignans, a class of polyphenols, are structurally similar to phenolic acids but contain a carbon-carbon bond within their biphenolic structure. These natural compounds are formed through the polymerization of two phenylpropane units and are distributed in various parts of plants, such as seeds, roots, stems, and leaves [1]. Lignans are classified into eight subgroups based on their carbon structure, ring formation patterns, and oxygen incorporation methods. These include furans, furofurans, aryl-naphthalenes, aryl-tetralins, and dibenzylbutyrolactones, with the position of the oxygen atom playing a key role in their classification [4][1]. Lignans represent the second most abundant biomass resource in the plant kingdom and are primarily composed of three types of phenylpropane units interconnected through ether and carbon-carbon bonds. Their structure is enriched with aromatic rings and active groups such as aromatic hydroxyl and quinone groups [4]. (Fig. 4C)

Lignans are commonly found in fiber-rich foods, including vegetables, legumes, and grains, and they are associated with numerous health benefits, particularly their anticancer activity through various mechanisms, as confirmed by multiple studies. Additionally, lignans exhibit anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anti-menopausal properties, contributing to the prevention of cardiovascular diseases, osteoporosis, and other psychological disorders [1]. Flaxseeds are among the richest sources of lignans and are increasingly used as dietary supplements. Plant lignans can be metabolized by gut microbiota into compounds such as enterodiol and enterolignans. According to a study by Bartkiene et al., consuming flaxseeds at a dose of 0.3 g/kg of body weight per day resulted in plasma concentrations of enterolignans and enterolactone of 65 and 20 nmol/L, respectively, underscoring the significance of these compounds in promoting health [8].

Figure 4. B) Chemical structural formulas of phenolic acids C) Chemical structure of lignin

3/ BIOAVAILABILITY OF POLYPHENOLS

The bioavailability of polyphenols is one of the crucial factors influencing their ability to produce biological effects in the body. Bioavailability refers to the amount that is absorbed through the digestive system and then enters the bloodstream, where it can affect target tissues. This process is influenced by multiple factors, including the ability of polyphenols to cross cell membranes, their chemical structure, size, as well as physiological factors such as previous diet, gender, gut microbiota composition, and the nutrient matrix.

The interaction of polyphenols with gut microbiota plays a significant role in stabilizing these compounds, as they are metabolized by gut bacteria to form metabolites such as glucuronides and sulfates, leading to a reduction in their bioavailability and effectiveness. This biological metabolism decreases the availability of polyphenols in their initial form and affects their antioxidant capacity. Additionally, environmental factors such as stomach pH, digestive enzymes, heat, light, and oxygen can affect the stability of polyphenols, potentially reducing their effectiveness and limiting their ability to reach the targeted biological site [1].

In general, the bioavailability of polyphenols is limited by four factors: I) Solubility. The hydrophilic nature of polyphenols is favorable for their bioavailability. For example, the oral absorption and bioavailability of quercetin can be significantly improved using a solubility-enhancing agent. II) Biotransformation. Polyphenols rarely exist in their original molecular structure after digestion with fermentation by gut microbes, but they mainly exist as metabolites. Current studies indicate that when measuring the bioavailability of polyphenols, their metabolites should also be considered. Biotransformation by gut microbes alters the original structure of polyphenols, thereby affecting their antioxidant capacity. III) Absorption. The ability of polyphenols to move from the stomach and intestines into the body plays an important role in their bioavailability [10].

On the other hand, recent studies have demonstrated the use of nanotechnology to improve the bioavailability of polyphenols, which may provide a promising solution to the challenge of efficiently absorbing these compounds in the body [12].

Some laboratory studies have shown that polyphenols in cannabis seeds have high bioavailability, with one study reporting that phenolic compounds had a bioavailability of 142.39% after digestion, while flavonoid compounds had a lower bioavailability of 29.47%. In another comparative study between wild Mexican blackberries and commercial blackberries, it was found that wild blackberries contained polyphenols with higher bioavailability and bioactivity compared to commercial blackberries. Furthermore, a study on silver coffee husk showed that the polyphenols in it could reach the targeted biological site after digestion and colonic fermentation, enhancing their ability to exert effective biological effects [1].

In conclusion, despite the potential health benefits of polyphenols, the challenges related to their bioavailability require further research into techniques for improving their absorption, such as using nanotechnology and encapsulation. These approaches may represent innovative solutions to improve the effectiveness of polyphenols as biologically active compounds in therapeutic and preventive applications [12].

4/ METHODS FOR EXTRACTION AND DETERMINATION OF POLYPHENOLS

Polyphenols are characterized by diverse phenolic structures, which grant them various chemical and physical properties that significantly influence their extraction methods. Selecting the appropriate extraction method is crucial, as it depends on the chemical composition of the target compound, the particle size of the sample, and potential interactions with other components used in the process. Additionally, extraction efficiency is a key factor in obtaining pure phenolic compounds. This efficiency is influenced by several parameters, including temperature, pH, the choice of solvent, the solvent-to-sample ratio, the number of extraction repetitions, and the extraction duration.

Despite the ongoing challenges in polyphenol analysis, developing accurate and sensitive methods for their extraction and determination is essential for advancing scientific research. Providing new data on the identity and quantities of polyphenols represents a fundamental step in understanding and evaluating their health benefits. [1]

4/1- ULTRASOUND-ASSISTED EXTRACTION

Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction (UAE) is considered one of the most efficient methods for extracting phenolic compounds due to its precision and high productivity within a very short time. This technique utilizes ultrasonic waves with frequencies above 20 kHz, making it effective for extracting both organic and inorganic compounds using liquid solvents. One of its advantages is being environmentally friendly, as it reduces extraction time, the volume of solvents used, and energy consumption. Ultrasonic waves cause damage to plant cell walls through a phenomenon known as cavitation, which occurs when sound waves pass through liquids, resulting in the formation of gas bubbles with high energy that release upon collapsing, creating hot spots that enhance the extraction of biologically active compounds. This process causes continuous expansion and contraction of the cells, increasing wall permeability and allowing solvents to easily access the cellular matrix and extract soluble compounds [1][2].

In recent years, this method has been used to extract polyphenols from various sources such as pecan shells, mango seeds, and olive residues, with a focus on improving the technique and studying the effects of the extracted polyphenols as antioxidants and antifungal agents [1].

In one study, ultrasound-assisted extraction proved effective in extracting phenols and flavonoids from mango peels. Moreover, subsequent nano-encapsulation enhanced the stability and bioavailability of the extract, making it suitable as a natural antioxidant additive in the food industry [13]. By comparison, the conventional method using aqueous alcoholic solvents (CSE-HA) is less efficient than ultrasound-assisted extraction, as it requires longer time and greater energy. Extraction parameters such as the solid-to-liquid ratio, temperature, and ethanol ratio in the solvent are controlled to obtain the final product [1].

The UAE technique was first applied in 1949 to extract oils from fish and their liver. Today, it is widely used across various industries due to its advantages, such as safety, time efficiency, and environmental compatibility. Additionally, this technique requires less energy compared to traditional methods like maceration or Soxhlet apparatus, and it significantly reduces carbon dioxide emissions. UAE is easy to implement, does not require high investment costs, and is suitable for industrial scalability.

Studies have shown that increasing the ultrasonic power improves the efficiency of polyphenol extraction, as demonstrated in the extraction of rosemary leaves using 130 W and sage using a 400 W device. Regarding amplitude, it has a nonlinear effect on the extracted content, with studies showing that the optimal amplitude depends on the type of targeted herbal material. Furthermore, the extraction duration significantly impacts efficiency; studies indicate an overall increase in polyphenol content over time, in line with Fick's second law of diffusion. However, prolonged extraction may lead to the degradation of active compounds due to thermal decomposition or polymerization.

Temperature is also a crucial factor, as moderate temperatures (up to 60°C) enhance extraction efficiency, whereas high temperatures may degrade compounds, although some studies highlight the positive effects of very high temperatures (80°C) in certain cases. Additionally, the type and polarity of the solvent greatly influence extraction efficiency, with aqueous alcoholic solvents being the most effective for extracting polyphenols compared to water or alcohol alone. These solvents improve the permeability of the solvent into the cellular matrix, making them the optimal choice [2].

FIGURE 5. SCHEME OF ULTRASOUND ASSISTED EXTRACTION OF HERBS.

4/2- MICROWAVE-ASSISTED EXTRACTION

Microwave-assisted extraction is an effective, green method for extracting polyphenols from plant samples such as herbs, plants, and other botanical materials. Generally, water is used as the solvent in this method, making it faster, cheaper, and more reliable compared to traditional methods. Optimizing the conditions affecting the extraction process is vital for achieving the best results, as the heat generated during the process significantly affects the production of the target polyphenols. The main factors influencing extraction efficiency include the type of solvent, its concentration, microwave power, and extraction time. These factors must be carefully controlled to ensure optimal sample enhancement and preservation of extracted compounds for maximum yield. [1][2][14][15]

Microwaves are electromagnetic radiation with wavelengths ranging from 1 cm to 1 meter and frequencies from 300 MHz to 300 GHz, placing them between radio waves and infrared radiation. Heating samples using microwaves relies on two concurrent phenomena: ionic conduction and dipole rotation. In ionic conduction, the varying electric field forces ions to move in opposite directions, resulting in ion collisions and heat generation. This process depends on the concentration and movement of ions within the sample. [2]

The basic microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) system consists of a magnetron to generate microwave energy, a shield to prevent energy backflow, a waveguide to direct the energy from the source to the cavity, and a stirrer to disperse the energy in multiple directions. Microwave systems for extracting bioactive compounds can come in two types: multimode or single-mode (focused). The type of vessel used in the extraction also plays a critical role in process efficiency, as it can be either closed or open. The closed system allows for processing multiple samples at once (typically between 8-14 samples), reduces the loss of volatile compounds, shortens extraction time, and requires significantly less solvent compared to the open system. [1][2]

Research studies indicate that polyphenols extracted by this method possess distinctive biological properties, such as antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anticancer activities. These studies have also shown that polyphenols can be extracted from waste and by-products, such as peels, residues, and leaves, in line with the "zero waste" policy. These extracted materials can be used for nutritional purposes or in the pharmaceutical industry. [1][14][15]

The effectiveness of microwave heating depends on the presence of polar materials or solvents capable of absorbing microwave radiation and converting it into heat. However, microwave radiation does not have the ability to directly break molecular bonds, as its energy is lower than what is needed to break the bonds. Microwave radiation is considered more efficient in heating samples compared to traditional heating techniques, as microwaves heat the entire sample in less time, while traditional heating requires heat to be transferred through the hot medium and then into the sample, which takes longer.

Extraction can be performed using microwaves without adding solvents, where water within the plant matrix is heated by microwave radiation. This results in increased pressure within the plant cells due to moisture evaporation, leading to the rapid rupture of plant membranes and an increase in the yield of extracted compounds. This method is known as solvent-free microwave extraction (SFME). In this method, the water within the plant cells acts as a solvent and contributes to the breakdown of cells. To protect heat-sensitive compounds, chemically stable media such as ionic liquids or graphite powder can be used to absorb microwaves without affecting the biological quality of the compounds. This method is called "improved solvent-free microwave extraction" (ISFME).

The microwave extraction process is characterized by significantly reduced extraction time (MAE compared to Soxhlet: 12 minutes versus 12 hours), energy savings (SFMAE compared to steam distillation: 144.10^3 kJ versus 270.10^4 kWh⁻¹), a smaller environmental footprint (MHG compared to steam distillation: 160 g of CO₂ versus 2400 g of CO₂), and a reduced solvent consumption (MAE compared to Soxhlet: 5 mL versus 100 mL). [2]

Recent studies show that using microwaves to extract polyphenols from plant materials offers numerous benefits that contribute to improved process efficiency and the quality of the extracted compounds. [1][2][14][15]

In a study conducted on papaya leaves, TPLP production increased with microwave power from 200 to 400 watts, while TPLP production decreased from 400 to 600 watts of microwave power. This indicates that an appropriate increase in microwave power for a short period was an effective method to enhance polyphenol extraction from papaya leaves due to accelerated polyphenol transport within cells (Alara, Abdurahman, & Olalere, 2018). However, excessive microwave power can reduce extraction yield. A similar trend was observed in ILMAE for polyphenols from *Peperomia pellucida* (L.) Kunth. This may be due to the fact that ionic liquids (ILs) effectively absorb microwave energy, and higher microwave radiation power increases the temperature, which could lead to the degradation of phenols. Therefore, 400 watts was considered the ideal microwave power for extracting TPL. [14]

In another study, a microwave system equipped with a Teflon vessel (Ethos LEAN, Sorisole, Italy) was used to extract polyphenols from corn cobs (*Zea mays* L.) using alcoholic aqueous solvents (MAE-HA). Briefly, 500 mg of CC powder was accurately weighed and placed in the extraction vessel. Extraction conditions were determined using experimental designs, considering the impact of four different parameters on polyphenol recovery from CC: SSR, T, EtOH% in aqueous alcohol mixtures, and irradiation time (t). The microwave power was initially set at 800 watts for 5 minutes to reach the target temperature, then reduced to 500 watts to maintain the samples at the extraction temperature. After a 10-minute ventilation period, each sample was filtered through filter paper. Ethanol was evaporated under vacuum at 37°C, and the remaining aqueous suspension was freeze-dried to obtain a solid product, similar to CSE. This method effectively improved polyphenol recovery compared to traditional methods. [15]

FIGURE 6 .SCHEME OF MICROWAVE ASSISTED EXTRACTION OF HERBS.

4/3- Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction (UAE) and Microwave-Assisted Extraction (MAE)

The combined technique of ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) and microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) represents a modern advancement that merges both methods to reduce extraction time and solvent consumption, leading to higher yields of bioactive compounds compared to using UAE or MAE alone. This approach involves heating the plant material using microwave waves, which helps release bioactive compounds through mild cell wall disruption, supported by ultrasound waves.

In a recent study, UAE and MAE were compared, with MAE showing higher polyphenol content and antioxidant activity, although it required a shorter extraction time. UAE, on the other hand, consumed less energy, making it more environmentally friendly. The results suggest that combining MAE and UAE could enhance polyphenol extraction efficiency and improve overall productivity.

In another study by Ma et al., ultrasound-assisted microwave extraction and enzyme-assisted ultrasound extraction were used to extract polyphenols from mangosteen peels. The findings indicated that the phenolic content was similar between both methods, but enzyme-assisted ultrasound extraction produced higher polyphenol yields compared to ultrasound-assisted microwave extraction. The polyphenols extracted using both methods demonstrated significant potential for application in the pharmaceutical and functional food additives industries. [1]

5/ THE MOST SIGNIFICANT THERAPEUTIC EFFECTS OF POLYPHENOLS

5/1-THE ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF POLYPHENOLS

The antioxidant activity of polyphenols is one of the most widely studied properties. One of the main characteristics of polyphenols is their ability to reduce or prevent reactive oxygen species (ROS), which are known for their role as antioxidants. Polyphenols have the ability to scavenge reactive oxygen species, which have harmful effects on human health. Therefore, polyphenols have demonstrated a protective role against stress or age-related diseases as well as skin degradation in humans [1][4][12]

Due to their structural composition, polyphenols interact with these reactive molecules primarily through three different mechanisms: hydrogen atom transfer (HAT), single electron transfer (SET), and transition metal chelation (TMC). In the HAT mechanism, the structure of polyphenols, including the functional phenolic group, enables them to donate a hydrogen atom by breaking the OH bond in hydroxyl molecules to a free radical. This mechanism is characterized by the bond dissociation enthalpy (BDE). With a lower BDE value for the OH bond, higher activity is expected, such as when the free radical R removes hydrogen atoms from the antioxidant ArOH ($R + ArOH = ArO + RH$).

In the SET mechanism, it is characterized by ionization potential (IP), and molecules with a low IP value indicate higher activity, through their ability to donate electrons, such as the electron-proton stripping from ArOH ($R + ArOH = R-AROH^+ = RH + ArO$). In the TMC mechanism, polyphenol anions have the ability to chelate heavy metals; therefore, due to the deprotonated hydroxyl structure, heavy metals can be chelated and then produce protons ($ArOH = ArO + H^+$). These three mechanisms provide polyphenols with the ability to protect human health from reactive species [1][10]

Studies show that some polyphenols, such as quercetin, have particularly strong antioxidant properties. Extensive studies have been conducted on polyphenols to investigate their antioxidant effects in laboratory and in vivo environments. For example, it was found that extracts from *Rhododendron tomentosum* contain compounds such as rosmarinic acid, caffeic acid, chlorogenic acid, rutin, and quercetin, and demonstrated strong radical scavenging activity using the DPPH assay. Another study by Menhem et al. showed that aqueous/ethanol flower extracts exhibited higher antioxidant activity compared to pure extracts. In a study conducted by Bashmil et al., unripe bananas showed a higher capacity for free radical scavenging compared to ripe bananas, with activity varying based on polyphenol composition.

C. angustifolium L. was also analyzed to assess its antioxidant activity, and it was found that fermentation affects its antioxidant capacity, which decreased after 24 hours but increased after 48 hours compared to non-fermented leaves. In another study, edible Fabaceae family flowers demonstrated antioxidant activity against nitric oxide and hydrogen peroxide, indicating their protective properties. Furthermore, coffee samples showed antioxidant roles, with activity differing depending on the growing region, as illustrated in a study by Bobkova et al. A study by Alsaud et al. indicated that the ethanolic extract of *Leptospermum scoparium* leaves exhibited higher antioxidant activity compared to extracts from other solvents [1]

Overall, polyphenols demonstrate their antioxidant effects by interacting with free radicals, inhibiting the activity of enzymes that cause their formation, chelating metals, and enhancing the activity of antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase and catalase [4][5][12]. Their activity measurement methods vary between chemical tests, cellular assays, and in vivo experiments.

The antioxidant activity measurement methods for polyphenolic compounds are divided into chemical tests, cell-based tests, and in vivo tests. Chemical tests include 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), 2,2'-azinobis-(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS), ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP), oxygen radical absorbance capacity (ORAC), and peroxy radical scavenging capacity (PSC), which are quick identification methods but have a significant gap in their mechanism compared to the internal response of the body. Cell-based tests are more consistent with biological interactions, but they still do not consider bioavailability. In vivo tests, typically using *Caenorhabditis elegans* or mice models, are more representative, but these methods are more complex and time-consuming. This review summarizes the antioxidant assessment methods for polyphenolic compounds and discusses their advantages and limitations, which may assist in distinguishing and selecting the appropriate test in the actual process, thus facilitating the development of comprehensive methods as well [10].

In conclusion, polyphenols represent an effective compound in protecting the body from oxidative stress, with immense potential for therapeutic and preventive applications against oxidation-related diseases [1][4][5][10][12]

5/2. ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY

Polyphenols, which possess a unique aromatic ring structure, have the ability to influence multiple inflammatory pathways. These compounds primarily act by inhibiting the expression and activity of pro-inflammatory mediators such as nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B), a key transcription factor in regulating the inflammatory response. It has been shown that polyphenols can inhibit the activation of NF- κ B, contributing to the reduction of pro-inflammatory cytokine and enzyme production. Through this mechanism, polyphenols exhibit anti-inflammatory effects by reducing the activation of multiple pathways related to inflammatory signaling. [1]

Inflammatory cytokines are a group of proteins whose primary role is to stimulate the inflammatory response and modulate immune responses in the body. When inflammation levels rise chronically within the organism, it can pose a significant threat to public health. Recent research suggests that polyphenols have the ability to effectively regulate inflammation. For example, Patni et al. discovered that the polyphenolic compound EGCG can alleviate inflammatory responses by upregulating the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-6 and downregulating the anti-inflammatory cytokine TNF- α , ultimately leading to reduced mTORC1 regulation. EGCG regulates inflammation through multiple pathways, including NF- κ B and PI3K-Akt-mTOR.

A study by Qiu et al. showed that terpene (TA) exhibits strong anti-inflammatory effects by suppressing the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6 in activated macrophage cells. Furthermore, polyphenolic compounds inhibit transcriptional activity in inflammatory responses, effectively preventing the expression of pro-inflammatory genes and thus exerting anti-inflammatory effects. For instance, polyphenols such as kaempferol significantly reduce the levels of proteins and mRNA for pro-inflammatory factors such as cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) and inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) in macrophage cells stimulated by lipopolysaccharide (LPS).

Additionally, Akanda et al. found that kaempferol alleviates oxidative stress induced by hydrochloric acid/ethanol by reducing lipid peroxidation and enhancing nitric oxide production. Kaempferol also significantly reduces the expression of TNF- α , IL-6, IL-1 β , iNOS, and COX-2, further promoting its anti-inflammatory effects. [4]

Oxidation often interferes with inflammatory responses, and polyphenols are believed to target these pathways effectively. For example, hydroxytyrosol (HT) has been shown to exert anti-inflammatory effects by regulating the NF- κ B pathway. HT effectively interrupts the activation of transcription factors such as NF- κ B, I- κ B α , and STAT-1 α , which play crucial roles in regulating the inflammatory response. Another study on the biological effects of phenolic extracts from olive oil on human monocyte cells (THP-1) demonstrated that polyphenols inhibit NF- κ B activation by preventing the nuclear translocation of NF- κ B p65 and DNA binding, thereby reducing the expression of oxidative stress-related genes (such as COX-2 and MMP9) and NF- κ B-related inflammatory factors like interleukin-1 and TNF- α . [16]

Laboratory studies have shown that polyphenols can also inhibit the production of pro-inflammatory lipid mediators, particularly by modulating the activity of enzymes involved in inflammatory processes such as nitric oxide (NO). Furthermore, polyphenols play an important role in modulating immune cell function, including macrophages, lymphocytes, and dendritic cells. Polyphenols are believed to affect immune cell activity, including their recruitment and migration, by modulating the expression of adhesion molecules and chemokines. Studies indicate that polyphenols may contribute to enhancing anti-inflammatory activity through synergistic interactions between different polyphenols, thus increasing their effectiveness.

Another study on the anti-inflammatory activity of polyphenols extracted from parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*), coriander (*Coriandrum sativum*), and celery (*Apium graveolens*) showed that parsley contains the highest total polyphenol content. When evaluating the activity of nitric oxide removal, a free radical produced in large amounts during various inflammatory conditions, polyphenols from parsley exhibited the highest activity and also demonstrated their ability to inhibit protein degradation and achieve anti-inflammatory effects. Additionally, parsley extracts were found to more effectively stabilize red blood cell membranes compared to the other plants in the study. [1]

On the other hand, mulberries contain rich polyphenols that have shown significant anti-inflammatory effects. A study conducted by Kim et al. on polyphenols extracted from the roots and unripe fruits of the black mulberry plant confirmed that these polyphenols can inhibit the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines and nitric oxide (NO) in LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 cells in a dose-dependent manner. Furthermore, black mulberry polyphenols were shown to reduce the mRNA levels of nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) and cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) enzymes in LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 cells, indicating their ability to decrease the expression of inflammation-associated enzymes. Additionally, black mulberry root polyphenols exhibited strong antimicrobial activity against pathogens such as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and *Bacillus anthracis*, further highlighting their significance as antimicrobial compounds.

Furthermore, studies have shown that polyphenols such as HT can inhibit the production of prostaglandin E2 (PGE2), which is involved in pathogenic mechanisms such as inflammation and increased vascular tension. HT significantly inhibits reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and COX-2 activation induced by LPS, contributing to the reduction of vascular inflammation. [1][16]

Polyphenols exert their anti-inflammatory effects by targeting MAPK cascades and reducing inflammatory interactions both in vivo and in vitro. For instance, studies have shown that quercetin reduces the phosphorylation of the mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR), ERK, and NF- κ B in fibroblast-like synoviocytes associated with rheumatoid arthritis (RA-FLS) induced by IL-17. In contrast, quercetin enhances the phosphorylation of AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) induced by IL-17, which is significant due to AMPK's role in inhibiting mTOR signaling. This dual effect suppresses mTOR and promotes apoptosis in osteoclasts, contributing to reduced inflammation and bone resorption. Furthermore, quercetin inhibits bone resorption by reducing the expression of interleukin-6 (IL-6) and matrix metalloproteinase-1 (MMP-1).

Similarly, myristin exhibited similar effects by inhibiting the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-1 β and suppressing the NF- κ B and mTOR pathways responsible for osteoclast formation and bone resorption, thus enhancing its role as an effective inhibitor of bone resorption. In the same context, EGCG was shown to target inflammatory factors and reduce phosphorylation levels in kinase proteins associated with the activation of growth factors such as endothelin and platelet-derived growth factor, ultimately leading to the inhibition of bone resorption and reducing inflammation. [12]

The effect of extra virgin olive oil on inflammatory cytokines was also measured in 66 participants over a period of 3 to 5 years. The results showed that extra virgin olive oil reduced levels of inflammatory molecules such as IL-6, TNF- α , and IFN- γ , promoting atherosclerosis stability. In another study on patients with metabolic syndrome, the consumption of extra virgin olive oil resulted in significant improvement in reducing postprandial inflammatory responses, with decreased activation of pathways such as NF- κ B, AP-1, and MAPKs, indicating strong anti-inflammatory effects. [16]

Finally, it is worth noting that resveratrol, another type of polyphenol, possesses anti-inflammatory properties by regulating cytokines. It enhances immune activity at low doses, while at high doses, it is associated with immunosuppressive effects. Additionally, quercetin, through its effect on cytokines, helps modulate gene expression related to bone remodeling and enhances anti-inflammatory effects. [12]

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this article aims to highlight the immense significance of polyphenols, not only as plant-derived compounds with potential therapeutic effects but also as tools that can reshape approaches to preventing and treating various chronic diseases. By exploring their classifications, properties, and mechanisms of action, it becomes evident that polyphenols offer vast prospects for developing effective and sustainable treatments.

Advances in polyphenol extraction techniques reflect the dedication of researchers to maximizing the benefits of these compounds while considering environmental and economic aspects. However, there remains an urgent need to deepen research on these compounds to better understand their potential and ensure their safe and effective applications.

Ultimately, this article serves as an invitation to researchers and decision-makers in the health field to invest in these promising compounds, whether through scientific studies or integrating them into prevention and treatment strategies, to enhance human health and improve the quality of life.

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